

COOPERATION BETWEEN BUSINESS AND LOCAL AUTHORITIES: PROBLEMS AND NEW OPPORTUNITIES

Khusan Atamuratovich Zhuraev

Termez State University Faculty
of Economics and tourism Uzbekistan

Abstract. The article is devoted to the study of the limitations and resources of interaction between government and business in modern conditions, the definition of the most popular and promising forms of cooperation. Based on this survey, the main risks are identified (the need for additional funding from the state, reputational losses in case of project failure or failure to achieve its goals, delays implementation of projects by the contractor) and barriers to the implementation of public partnership practices (lack of opportunities to provide motivation for private investment, business disinterest). It is concluded that the existing dysfunctions of the institutional field do not allow creating a basis for normatively fixed practices of partnership between government and business, and state partnership becomes a utopia for municipalities. The most promising form of interaction between government and business is the economy of cooperation as an effective tool for the socio-economic development of the territory. At the same time, the conditions for the implementation of a new form of interaction between the public and private sectors should be an active and flexible position of local authorities, an analysis of the interests and needs of the business community, and the effective use of state property. The principles of the economy of cooperation can be adapted and used in the context of the socio-economic development of the territories.

Key words: public-private partnership; local governments; small and medium business; business community; the economics of cooperation; state organizations.

INTRODUCTION. Currently, in the context of the economic crisis, the contradiction that arises between the state and the public sector is especially acute, which consists in the fact that the state seeks to provide citizens with public goods, and the priorities of the business community are shifted towards making a profit. At the same time, the possibility of establishing partnerships between business and government with the provision of greater opportunities for the business sector to

participate in the provision of social services to the population largely depends on the degree of maturity of civil society and the development of public institutions.

Public-private partnership practices are often characterized by a shift in the balance of interests, which leads to mistrust of the main subjects of the partnership. The disposition of state power acts in these conditions as administrative-distributive, business - selfishly consumer. Representatives of authorities in their activities use exclusively administrative mechanisms, and business is focused on making a profit. As a result, as noted by I.P. Babintsev (2016), there is a “discrepancy between the dispositions of the actors”, due to a high level of mistrust towards each other.

In world practice, recently, one of the forms of economic relations based on trust has become the economy of cooperation (sharing economy). According to experts, this form of interaction is “one of the ten ideas that will turn the world upside down” (Cauffman, Smits, 2016). The collaborative economy, according to some scholars (see, for example: Hira, Reilly, 2017), contains transformational potential for many other sectors of the economy, as well as opportunities for new entrepreneurial activity and growth in the developing world.

In particular, the UK predicts the growth of the cooperation economy by 2025 to 9 billion pounds sterling⁴. This model assumes the willingness of the owner to share resources that are underutilized (from skills and abilities to premises) with those who need them. This form of relationship stimulates new forms of cooperation and new technologies that allow the population to access a variety of resources by transferring them free of charge, renting or sharing.

Today, there are various business models within the collaborative economy. Basically, they are a platform for human-to-human (P2P), business-to-business (B2B) or business-to-people (B2P) interaction.

This is due to the fact that an excess resource, as a rule, is observed among citizens or entrepreneurs, however, its presence is also typical for authorities that own municipal institutions and sites that have great opportunities for their additional use.

In foreign practice, there are open libraries, public schools or museums that offer their services to the needs of the local community. In addition, a movement of cities appeared, ready to develop the principles of the economy of cooperation on their territories.

Unfortunately, in our country, unlike developed democratic countries, there has not yet been a model of interaction between government and business, built on a balance of interests and partnership. In modern conditions, only the mutual interest of authorities and business representatives can become the basis of their partnerships. With the help of such a combination of efforts, it is possible to ensure a single economic space, create a favorable business climate, and form a middle class (Bidzhiev, 2012).

Thus, the current conditions for the development of society, the crisis state of the economy, the urgent need for private investment actualize the search for new forms of cooperation between business and government, based on mutual trust, a balance of interests.

The purpose of this article is to study the limitations and resources of interaction between government and business, to determine the most popular and promising forms of cooperation in modern conditions.

Public-private partnership in modern conditions: reality or utopia?

Cooperation between authorities and the business community is characterized by a wide range of interaction practices: from attracting financial resources from organizations on a gratuitous basis to the implementation of public-private

partnership projects. Between these poles there are such forms of interaction as short-term contracts for the performance of a certain type of work, the provision of public services, service agreements for the repair and operation of social infrastructure facilities, joint ventures (the share of private capital as a shareholder in a state enterprise).

Public-private and public-private partnerships are among the legislatively fixed forms of cooperation between government and business in our country. The adoption of the relevant federal law created the legal basis for the integration of public partners in the socio-economic development of the territory.

Reference

1. Bleyman N. (2017) The digital dividend. URL: <http://www.rbcplus.ru/news/59ef050d7a8aa91b5266834d>.
2. Murodovna, R. G. (2021). Analytical procedure in an audit of fixed assets. International Journal of Financial Management and Economics International Journal of Financial Management and Economics, 4(1), 41-45P.
3. Rahimova G. (2021). Accounting of the results of continuous revaluation of property, plant and equipment in accordance with international standards. Society and innovations, (Общество и инновации) (Жамият ва ва инновациялар) 3(2021) / ISSN 2181-1415.
4. Rakhimova G. (2021). The main instrument of calculation is the theoretical justification of the stratification of flour into the current state and people's standards./ International multidisciplinary scientific conferences on the DIALOGUE BETWEEN SCIENCE & ARTS, RELIGION/ 65-67 P.
5. Fleetwood S. Sketching a socio-economic model of labour markets // Cambridge Journal of Economics. 2011. Vol. 35. № 1. P. 15—38.
6. Murynov A.A. Taxation of sub-federal securities and local government financial flows. <https://cyberleninka.ru>.
7. Novikov A. 1997. Instruments of the municipal securities market abroad // Securities market. № 4. p. 25-30.